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**The ladder of Information
Management towards the future.**

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- Information Management and the life cycle of information
- Information professional
 - Reactive professional
 - Change to a proactive professional
- Information Governance

- **Wilson, T.D.** "Information management", in *International Encyclopedia of Information and Library Science*
 - "The application of management principles **to the acquisition, organization, control, dissemination and use** of information relevant to the effective operation of organizations of all kinds.
 - 'Information' here refers to **all types of information of value**, whether having their origin inside or outside the organization, including data resources, such as production data; records and files related, for example, to the personnel function; market research data; and competitive intelligence from a wide range of sources.
 - Information management deals with the **value, quality, ownership, use and security of information** in the context of organizational performance."

- Macevičiūtė, Elena and Wilson, T.D. (2002) "The development of the information management research area" ***Information Research***, 7 (3) Available at: <http://InformationR.net/ir/7-3/paper133.html>
 - "...although information management **draws upon ideas from both librarianship and information science**. In one form or another it is likely to persist in the future, since information problems are likely to persist in organizations. **The means for resolving the problems may change, but the need to understand those problems and develop solutions will remain.**"
 - "Perhaps we shall re-visit this topic in a few years' time to discover whether we are right."

(Extended) Life Cycle of Information; Wilson

- Identification of information needs.
- Study of information behavior.
- Information audit.
- New professional profile within the "Information Management": INFORMATION GOVERNOR

- Reactive / Static information professional
 - works on demand,
 - not very interested in other aspects of the organization.
 - *It is like the "independent republic of the record management"*
- New manager, Proactive manager.

- FESABID, Spanish Federation of Societies of Archivists, Librarians, Documentalists and Museologists.
- FESABID study on information professionals, 2011
- Prospective of an evolving profession.
 4. The vision of the experts.

Problems related to the professionals.

 - ... **The lack of proactivity** in the detection and occupation of new niches

Opportunities for the changing needs of users.

 - The growing social perception of increase, diversify and overload of information and content
 - Mobility

- The last step. Information Governance
- Professional role
 - someone really close to levels of decision,
 - how much information, in what format and frequency, by what means,...
- KPMG or Deloitte, are recommending their clients to incorporate these professionals
 - where are formed these professionals?

- “Gobernanza”, “governança”
 - *RAE: “**art or manner of governing** that has as objective the achievement of sustainable economic, social and institutional development, promoting a healthy balance between state, civil society and markets ... ”*

*Maquiavelli, perhaps the best in
information governance ...*

- Something new, is it a discipline or just a fad?.
- It is a concept to consolidate because:
 - (1) meets a real need: a lack of information governance beyond the ICTs;
 - (2) are words with clear meaning , direct and easy to understand;
 - (3) Implies a decisive rupture with the tendency to emphasize the continent - ICTs -with respect to content;
 - (4) has a semantic relationship with concepts used in our society (and always present) as "good governance", "global governance", "economic governance" ...
- Information placed in strategic context of organizations, directive areas of control and decision.

- Information Governance: Life cycle (Anderson)

● Quarkside...

- **Why** are we **doing** it and what are the **constraints**?
- What do we expect the **benefits** to be and how can we **measure** them?
- **Who** has to do and who will be the **beneficiaries**?
- What are our **information assets** and what **level of access and control** we have?
- What is the **entire process** of "inception - validation - storage and deletion" of information?
- What are the main **risks** of the information and what are the plans for reducing them?
- Do we know **when** things should happen?
- And definitely, is our **level of maturity** sufficient to undertake a process in this field?

*we must not be governed only
by computer techs...
can make our lives a little less
beautiful and interesting ...
it's better read and walk*

"who walks much and reads much, knows much and sees much" (Don Quixote)
(quien anda mucho y lee mucho, sabe mucho y ve mucho).

